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Enhanced Structural Performance of Additively Manufactured 2D-lattice Sandwich with Tailored Fiber Orientation using Hot Powder Bed Compaction

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Overview

- Introduction
- HPBC process overview
- Material, LSS design and characterization tests
- Progressive damage modeling
- Results and analysis
- Conclusion

Additive manufacturing and flexible consolidation process

Material extrusion (MEX) process

- Co-printed skin and truss core
- Trussed aligned fiber
- Doesn't required mold
- **Poor consolidation**

Hot powder bed compaction LSS consolidation under hydrostatic compaction

- **HPBC provides the synergy between traditional compression molding (good for consolidation but required for specific mold) and MEX process (doesn't required mold but poor consolidation)**

Compression molding or Autoclave curved

- Good consolidation
- **Multi-step process**
- **Required multi-assembly mold**

Hot powder bed compaction process

- **Powder Densification Stage:** Fine talc powder serves as a flexible medium, compacted under 1-2 tons (~500 kPa axial pressure) of load for 10 minutes.
- **Heating Stage:** Mold was heated in a convection oven to 223°C (endset of PA6 melt enthalpy) 140 minutes.
- **Consolidation of MEX part during cool-down:** During cooling, continuous compressive force was maintained, allowing molten matrix flow and void closure, improving part consolidation.
- This process supports complex geometries from subtractive manufacturing, MEX topology-optimized parts, and lattice sandwich structures.

MEX lattice structure

Subtractive manufacturing

MEX topologically optimized rocker

Material and mechanical characterization test

- Material: Fiber reinforced nylon (PA6)
 - SCF: 10.5% fiber volume fraction
 - LCF: 45% fiber volume fraction
- Microscopy analysis
 - Void distribution analysis
- Mechanical Test:
 - Tensile coupon test
 - Sandwich structure 3PB test
- DSC Analysis
 - Crystallinity fraction
 - Enthalpy of melting

Types of tensile specimen based on LCF orientation

Section A-A

2D-LSS design

- Two truss core configuration with same beam height, core density and LCF volume fraction
 - $N_r = 4 \rightarrow$ 4-row core with 2.2 mm trusses with 1 LCF tow per truss
 - $N_r = 2 \rightarrow$ 2-row core with 4.4 mm trusses with 2 LCF tow per truss
- Both configurations had 2 LCF tows in top and bottom skins
- Same A/l_t ratio ensured constant axial rigidity of trusses across designs.
- The design ensured that structure performance differences between pre- and post-HPBC LSS resulted solely from material and microstructural changes, not geometry variations.

	Pristine (mm)		HPBC (mm)	
	$N_r = 4$	$N_r = 2$	$N_r = 4$	$N_r = 2$
h	28.4	28.4	28.25	29.35
b	15	15	12.28	12.36
t₁	6	12	5.92	11.89
t₂	12	24	12.21	24.37
t_h	2.2	4.4	2.75	5.63
t_s	2.2	2.2	2.19	2.19
s	144	144	146.13	146.23
A/l_t	3.89	3.89	4.03	4.14
I₃₃/l_t² (mm²)	0.18	0.37	0.3	0.65

Lattice structure geometry

Tailored fiber orientation in truss direction

Parametric geometry of LSS

Effective homogenized post-HPBC SCF and LCF properties

- A microstructure-based finite element approach using Digimat-FE was used to anisotropic homogenize the SCF layer properties.
- Microscopy analysis was used to determine a void fraction of 3.1% and a fiber length distribution of 0.098 ± 0.014 mm.
- During the MEX process, short fibers tend to align in the direction of material deposition due to shear-induced flow, resulting in a non-random fiber orientation distribution (FOD).
- Homogenized anisotropic LCF layer properties were predicted using a hybrid micromechanical model considering contributions from both continuous and highly aligned long discontinuous fibers with weight average of 0.5:0.5.

Modified Halpin–Tsai model

Table 1: Homogenized stiffness and strength properties

Material property	SCF	LCF
Longitudinal modulus, E_{11} (GPa)	6.41	86
Transverse modulus, E_{22} (GPa)	6.41	5.1
Through-thickness modulus, E_{33} (GPa)	3.11	5.1
In-plane shear modulus, G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	0.88	3.2
Out-of-plane shear modulus, G_{23} (GPa)	0.78	960
In-plane poisson's ratios, ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.28	0.25
Out-of-plane poisson's ratios, ν_{23}	0.33	0.38
Longitudinal tensile strength, σ_{1t} (MPa)	110	1150
Longitudinal compressive strength, σ_{1c} (MPa)	230	1900
Transverse tensile strength, σ_{2t} (MPa)	110	80
Transverse compressive strength, σ_{2c} (MPa)	230	180
Transverse shear strength, τ_{12} (MPa)	80	150
Fracture energy in fiber, G_{11} (kJ/m ²)	6	12
Fracture energy in matrix, G_{22} (kJ/m ²)	2	4
Viscosity regularization in fiber, η_f	0.001	0.001
Viscosity regularization in fiber, η_m	0.001	0.001

FEA modeling of tensile coupons and LSS components

- A homogenized LCF layer was sandwiched between two $[+45^\circ/-45^\circ]$ oriented homogenized SCF layers.
- The LCF layer were aligned in the truss direction to capture actual fiber orientation during MEX deposition.
- Anisotropic linear elastic material was assigned at roller contact regions to avoid damage due to stress concentrations.
- The sandwich structure was meshed with finer elements (0.3 mm \times 0.3 mm) in the central 48 mm region and coarser mesh (0.3 mm \times 0.6 mm) elsewhere, with 0.125 mm thickness through all layers.

Modelling of LCF layer with SCF walls

LCF-PD
 LCF-LE
 SCF-PD
 SCF-LE

LCF orientation in truss direction

Skin
 Unit cell

Tensile coupon cross section

Continuum damage mechanics model

- A strain-based CDM model was implemented in ABAQUS using UMAT subroutine.
- The framework captured nonlinear fiber and matrix damage progression, enabling accurate prediction of stiffness degradation and damage progression
- HPBC-treated dogbone specimens exhibited the following properties:
 - Elastic modulus: 25.5 ± 0.61 GPa (longitudinal), 6.93 ± 0.22 GPa (transverse)
 - Tensile strength: 285.66 ± 4.83 MPa (longitudinal), 101.69 ± 1.43 MPa (transverse)

$$f_1^2 = \frac{(\epsilon_{11})^2}{\epsilon_{11}^f \epsilon_{11}^c} + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{11}}{\epsilon_{11}^f} - \frac{\epsilon_{11}}{\epsilon_{11}^c} \right)$$

$$f_2^2 = \frac{(\epsilon_{22})^2}{\epsilon_{22}^f \epsilon_{22}^c} + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{22}}{\epsilon_{22}^f} - \frac{\epsilon_{22}}{\epsilon_{22}^c} \right) + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{12}}{\epsilon_{12}^f} \right)^2$$

$$f_3^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{33}}{F_{3z}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{13}}{F_{sz}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{23}}{F_{sz}} \right)^2$$

$$d_i = 1 - \frac{\epsilon_{ii}^{ft}}{f_i} e^{\left(\frac{C_{ii}^{ft} (\epsilon_{ii}^{ft} - f_i) \times l_c}{G_i} \right)}; \quad i = 1, 2$$

$$d_3 = \begin{cases} 0, & f_3 < 1 \\ 0.95, & f_3 \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

$$\sigma_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_1)C_{11}^0 & (1-d_1)(1-d_2)C_{12}^0 & (1-d_1)C_{13}^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & (1-d_2)C_{22}^0 & (1-d_2)(1-d_3)C_{23}^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & (1-d_3)C_{33}^0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & (1-d_1)(1-d_2)C_{44}^0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & (1-d_3)C_{55}^0 & 0 \\ & & & & & (1-d_3)C_{66}^0 \end{bmatrix} \times \epsilon_{ij}$$

sym.

Microscopic analysis of post-HPBC sandwich beam

- The improved microstructure exhibited void content less than 2.3% and improved consolidation, with consistent shrinkage for both HPBC-treated LSS. A 17.8% reduction in width (Z-direction) and 26.4% increase in truss thickness were observed.

Pristine $N_r = 4$ and $N_r = 2$ lattice sandwich structure micrographs

HPBC $N_r = 4$ and $N_r = 2$ lattice sandwich structure micrographs

V_{11} : inter LCF-SCF layer void, V_{12} : intra SCF layer void, V_{13} : intra LCF layer void, V_{14} : intra LCF-SCF layer void

— LCF
— SCF

Y
Z (build)

Failure analysis of LSS with DIC Y- displacement

- DIC full-field displacement analysis revealed failure modes including localized skin yielding and truss buckling in LSS.
- Higher I_{33}/I_{t2} ratio in the $N_r = 2$ configuration provided higher critical truss buckling load, increasing skin yielding load
- Pristine failure initiated at the tensile-side skin, propagating through the core along weak LCF–SCF interface voids.
- HPBC-treated samples showed only localized skin yielding and no truss deformation in $N_r = 4$ and $N_r = 2$.
- Performance improvements were mainly due to microstructural changes like better interlayer fusion and void reduction, not phase transformation or crystallinity fraction (HPBC : $27.67 \pm 1.33\%$; Pristine: $33.49 \pm 0.18 \%$), as confirmed by the DSC results.

Test results and progressive damage analysis of LSS

- Both pristine LSS configurations showed similar unit width stiffness ($\sim 111.6 \pm 4.4 \text{ N/mm}^2$); however, $N_r = 2$ exhibited 425.1 N/mm, 30% higher strength compared to $N_r = 4$
- Post-HPBC, stiffness improved by 122% for both configurations;
 - Strength of $N_r = 2$ increased by 86%, while $N_r = 4$ showed a 154% stiffness gain
- The FEA predicted a stiffness of 265.3 N/mm^2 and strength of 689.8 N/mm.
- Crack initiation at the tension-side skin and progression into the core, was demonstrated through fiber direction stress (σ_{11}) evolution during damage propagation.

Conclusion

- HPBC process **improved LSS strength** by 154% and **stiffness** by 119%, without the need for rigid tooling.
- Tailored LCF–SCF reinforcement enabled **effective consolidation** in two complex cores geometry, reducing voids below 2.3%.
- DIC analysis showed failure shifted from **truss-induced skin yielding (pristine)** to **skin failure (HPBC)** post HPBC process.
- **Meso-scale CDM-based FEA approach** closely predicted stiffness, strength, and crack progression.
- A consistent **17.8% Z-direction shrinkage** was observed, enabling predictable geometry control during design.
- Combining HPBC with MEX offers a scalable, cost-efficient route for **fabricating complex, high-performance composites**.

Thank You

(Question, suggestion and comments)